

"MEASURES TAKEN DURING THE PERIOD OF SHORTAGE OF FODDER HAY"

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the problem of harvesting and processing hay up to 85% of the feed given as raw feed for farm animals. Much attention is paid to the use of various methods in the preparation of roughage, as well as the effectiveness of their use in feeding livestock with roughage. Because 45% of the feed used consists of forage hay. The introduction of fodder hay production technology into the national economy is one of the urgent tasks today.

Key words: fodder, hay, fodder, grain, rice husk, camel thorn.

"МЕРЫ, ПРИНИМАЕМЫЕ В ПЕРИОД ДЕФИЦИТА КОРМОВОГО СЕНА"

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена проблеме заготовки и переработки сена до 85 % корма, выдаваемого в качестве сырого корма для сельскохозяйственных животных. Большое внимание уделено использованию различных приемов при заготовке грубых кормов, а также эффективности их использования при кормлении скота грубыми кормами. Потому что 45% используемого корма состоит из фуражного сена. Внедрение технологии производства фуражного сена в народное хозяйство является одной из актуальных задач на сегодняшний день.

Ключевые слова: фураж, сено, корм, зерно, рисовая шелуха, верблюжья колючка.

INTRODUCTION

The period of feed shortage falls mainly in winter. It is at this time that the animals in the herd are fed with coarse feed. When preparing coarse feeds, straw, hay, corn husk, rice husk, natural herbs, and cane are used in the feed base of compound feeds. Oatmeal, salt and other raw nutrients play an extremely important role. High-calorie feeds are a source of energy proteins, vitamins and other vital elements for the animal body.

Balanced feeding of animals with some other additives and elements is very effective.

Among all cattle, more feed is consumed per unit of cattle production. For example, 1 kg of beef takes 2 times more feed than 1 kg of pork, and 3 times more than poultry.

At the same time, ruminants have a better ability to absorb raw nutrients by body tissues than others. Such feeds include straw and hay.

Per 1 kg of dry matter, straw contains the same amount of energy as concentrates. However, this energy is mainly stored in fiber, it is difficult to convert and, as a result, difficult to digest.

Therefore, straw must be recycled. Preparing livestock for laying straw and other plant residues for the winter is a complex process. Straw protein is characterized by low overall nutritional value and physical properties.

In the practice of feeding cattle, there are 2 ways of harvesting straw.

1. On the physico-chemical and biological effects on straw.
2. Decoration and use in the form of briquettes.

Feeding cattle with physically processed straw. This is the simplest and most widely used method in practice. This includes shredding straw, wetting, steaming, and so on.

Crushed straw facilitates the preparation of feed for cattle. Completely eaten cheap fowls. The crushed straw is well moistened and mixed. Do not overdo it. The reason is that chewed straw is poorly digested, and the recovery of chewing in cattle is slow. Horses have cases of colic. The length of the sheared straw should be 4-5 cm for cattle and 2-3 cm for horses and sheep.

It is recommended to use the crushers JAGUAR 900, 960,830 and the best NEW Holland TL-100, Belarus-100. Finely prepared straw should be stored indoors.

Moisten the chopped straw. For moisten the crushed straw, hot salt water, bar, feed molasses are used (1.5-2 kg of salt per 100 kg of straw is dissolved in 80-100 liters of water for 20-300 seconds). Straw consumption is increasing. . Sufficiently moistened straw should not let water through when squeezed by hands. Straw can be stored in cemented bags or in large containers. Immediately after the end of soaking should be given to cattle, when added to the roots, silage, bar soaked straw improves its consumption and has a positive effect on digestion.

Moistening of straw. Put the crushed straw in layers in large bowls or bags, moisten evenly with water (80-100 liters of water per 1 liter of straw) and press, sprinkle with salt or add other nutrients. A bowl or wrapper filled with straw is sealed and steam is supplied. Steaming lasts 30-40 minutes after steam starts to come out from under the lid. After that, they are left to cool down a little for 6-8 hours and given to cattle. For dairy cattle, dairy cows, it is preferable to use steamed straw.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The method of using straw is to dissipate heat by itself. This is the most convenient way, which does not require fuel. At the same time, the crushed straw is soaked in pots or seams (1.5 m wide, 1.5 m deep, 4-room ditches, depending on the length). Straw 25-30 cm thick is poured into each room, each layer is moistened with 20-30 liters of water at the rate of 65-70 liters per 100 kg and mixed well. To accelerate the spontaneous heating of straw, 30-40 liters of boiling water are poured from each place and well tamped. After 3-4 days, as a result of fermentation in the straw, it begins to heat up, and its temperature reaches 40-500 ° C. To do this, use high-quality autumn straw that does not contain mold and rot bacteria.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Chemical treatment of straw. Chemical treatment of straw is most effective, and its digestion depends on the amount of lignin, silicic acid, etc., present in it in large quantities. These substances are not only indigestible, but also make it difficult to assimilate nutrients. The main purpose of chemical treatment is the partial cleavage of lignins by silicic acids and the reduction of their resistance. Under the influence of chemicals (alkaline dilutions), pectin dissolves, the crust on the fabric softens slightly. Physico-chemical changes of straw during alkali treatment, strength of alkaline liquid. It depends on the temperature, the duration of processing and the nature of the straw. At the same time, ruminants digest up to 68-72% of organic substances, up to 80-82% of fiber, up to 55-65% of nitrogen-free extractives. Without processing, it absorbs 45% of organic substances, 53-55% of fiber and 40% of nitrogen-free extractives.

Biological methods of straw preparation. As mentioned above, it is also effective to feed cattle without chemical treatment of raw feed.

As a result of hydrolysis of straw and its protein enrichment, the nutrient content increases by 2.5-3 times.

Recently, the hydrolysis of straw by injection treatment with yeast has become widespread. This gives a certain amount of sugar, 5-20% of dry vegetable mass and various sugars.

The second part of straw processing is the cultivation of feed yeast using hydrolyzed straw or other coarse feed processed into sugar. When processing one ton of dry straw with yeast, 200-250 kg of dry yeast is obtained. One kg of dry yeast contains 350 kg of digestible protein. Calculations show that the cost of by-products obtained from food yeast is 1.5-2 times higher than the cost of yeast used in dairy farming.

For prepare one ton of hydrolyzed yeast mass, the following is required.

1. 80 kg of straw flour.
2. 50 kg of crushed concentrates.
3. 1.5 kg of ammonium sulfate salt.
4. 2 kg of fluoride-free phosphoric acid or 3 kg of phosphate-calcium salt.
5. 650 kg of water
6. 120 kg of steam
7. 100 kg of yeast, i.e. 43 kg of rye or barley flour.

DISCUSSION

Straw silage. This is one of the biological methods that can be applied anywhere. At the beginning of silage, the bottom of the trenches is covered with crushed straw 30-50 cm thick. Thus, the undivided straw is laid in layers 20-30 cm thick. Each layer of straw is sprayed with a prepared solution (0,6-0,8 1,0-1,5 per 1 ton) to a humidity of 65%. The solution in the cans is sprayed by a pump. At the same time, the silage mass is constantly plowed by heavy tractors (T-130, T-150, etc.). After 3-5 days of extinguishing, it is necessary to soak for another 6-8 hours. Feeding straw for silage to cattle should be set at lower rates: 2-3 kg per day for cattle and 0.3-0.5 kg for sheep. Then up to 30% of dry matter can be added to the diet of cattle. Dry bacterial drops should be stored in a cooler place (preferably in the refrigerator).

CONCLUSION

In agriculture, up to 85% of straw is used mainly as feedstock. Forty-five percent of coarse feed for livestock is straw. Therefore, it is necessary to apply the technology of straw harvesting on the farm.

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